

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets

D9.3 Cooperation Activities

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
ABM	Agent-based Modelling
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation
COM-B	Capability, Opportunity, Motivation, and Behaviour
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DEAP	Digital Education Action Plan
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DR-Flex	Demand Response for energy Flexibility
DSR	Demand Side Response
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
EIT	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
FaaS	Flexibility as a Service
GBP	Generic Business Processes
GPFM	Green Powered Future Mission
HEMS	Home Energy Management Systems
IoT	Internet of Things
ISGAN	International Smart Grid Action Network
KIC	Knowledge and Innovation Communities
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NLP	Natural Language Processing
PF	Postdoctoral Fellowship
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SE	Staff Exchange
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
WG	Working Group

CONSORTIUM

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2 (Partner)	Cleanwatts Digital SA	CWD	PT
3 (Partner)	EPRI Europe DAC	EEU	IE
4 (Partner)	SSE Airtricity LTD	SSEA	IE
5 (Partner)	DCSix Technologies Limited	DCS	IE
6 (Partner)	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	DK
7 (Partner)	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY	VTT	FI
8 (Partner)	AKKA High Tech – Akkodis Group	AKKO	FR
8.1 (Affiliated)	AKKA I&S	AKKIS	FR
8.2 (Affiliated)	MODIS France	MODIS	FR
9 (Partner)	Universidad de Castilla - La Mancha	UCLM	ES
10 (Partner)	Agenzia Nazionale per le Nuove Tecnologie, L'energia e lo Sviluppo Economico Sostenibile	ENEA	IT
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable provides an analysis of the EU-DREAM project's cooperation activities during its first year, evidencing the project's central role in catalysing digital and green transformation across Europe's energy sector. EU-DREAM brings together a diverse consortium of research, industry, and innovation partners, with the shared ambition of empowering consumers and communities to become active participants in the energy transition through next-generation digital technologies.

Scope and Methodology:

D9.3 covers the full range of cooperation activities involving EU-DREAM, spanning project clustering, joint research, knowledge exchange, and engagement with European initiatives and policy instruments. The report's findings are based on systematic tracking of project meetings, surveys, event participation, shared outputs, and feedback from partners. The deliverable documents not only completed actions but also ongoing and planned collaboration, providing a living picture of EU-DREAM's networking impact and strategic positioning.

Key Cooperation Domains:

- **E-ENERGY Cluster:**

EU-DREAM is a member of the E-ENERGY cluster, an alliance of five Horizon Europe projects (EU-DREAM, ENERGENIUS, DIGITISE, DECODIT, CELINE) dedicated to digital innovation and consumer empowerment. This cluster has demonstrated pioneering practices in joint branding, communication, and the co-development of digital tools. Regular coordination meetings, open communication channels, and shared outreach events have enabled effective alignment of methodologies, cross-promotion of activities, and the creation of impactful resources for citizen engagement.

- **BRIDGE Initiative:**

As an active participant in the European Commission's BRIDGE initiative, EU-DREAM contributes to and benefits from a European ecosystem of over 200 projects focused on smart grids, energy storage, islands, and digitalisation. The project's work in all four BRIDGE Working Groups (Business Models, Regulation, Consumer and Citizen Engagement, and Data Management) has positioned EU-DREAM as an important contributor in AI-driven business models, regulatory innovation, inclusive engagement, and data interoperability. Notable achievements include contributions to surveys and best practice exchanges, chairing and co-leading working group actions, and piloting consumer-centric tools and strategies for flexibility, peer-to-peer energy sharing, and stakeholder participation.

- **Synergies with Other EU Initiatives and Instruments:**

EU-DREAM has proactively established links with a wide range of other EU-level actions and frameworks. This includes active engagement in the Erasmus+ Programme (for capacity building, digital education, and training), collaboration with Digital Innovation Hubs (supporting SME digitalisation and regional innovation), and alignment with the European Climate Pact and Digital Education Action Plan (advancing climate literacy, social inclusion, and digital skills). The consortium is also strategically preparing for deeper involvement with Horizon Europe instruments such as ERC, MSCA, EIT KICs, and the Green Powered Future Mission, leveraging

the project's unique living labs and open digital platforms to foster cross-sectoral research, experimentation, and knowledge transfer.

Strategic Achievements and Lessons Learned:

- EU-DREAM's approach to cooperation demonstrates the added value of structured project clustering, cross-project benchmarking, and coordinated dissemination to scale up innovation and impact.
- Participation in working groups and joint actions has enabled the project to help shape EU policy recommendations, accelerate technology adoption, and inform the development of standards for interoperability, user engagement, and data governance.
- The integration of AI, digital twin, and user-centric approaches across living labs has provided robust environments for piloting and validating solutions, feeding practical insights into both technical progress and social innovation.
- Lessons learned point to the importance of ethical and inclusive design, stakeholder empowerment, and continuous knowledge exchange, for project success and for system-wide transformation.

Outlook and Next Steps

Building on these foundations, EU-DREAM will further expand its cooperation footprint in the coming period by:

- Scaling up living lab activities and cross-border pilot initiatives.
- Strengthening engagement with policy and industry networks for the digitalisation of energy systems.
- Deepening partnerships with educational, climate, and research bodies to mainstream digital skills and citizen empowerment.
- Systematically disseminating best practices, tools, and methodologies for replication across Europe.

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Introduction

EU-DREAM is dedicated to empowering European citizens with innovative digital technologies for the energy transition. By integrating cutting-edge solutions such as Digital Twins (DT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Natural Language Processing (NLP), the project enables both consumers and communities to take an active role in energy management, market participation, and flexibility services provision [1]. The project's mission aligns closely with the European Union's (EU) vision of a just and inclusive energy transition, supporting easy access to digital energy services, fostering energy literacy, and advancing social innovation.

This deliverable presents an overview of the cooperation activities carried out within the EU-DREAM project during the first project year, with a particular focus on their role in supporting both the project's objectives and the broader priorities of the European Union. The main purpose of this report is to document, analyse, and reflect on the EU-DREAM's extensive engagement with EU-wide collaboration platforms. This includes diverse cooperation efforts undertaken with complementary EU projects, especially in the context of the E-ENERGY Cluster [2], the BRIDGE initiative [3], which is an initiative to foster collective knowledge and address common challenges faced by Horizon Europe projects working in the field of smart energy systems.

In addition to these core areas of collaboration, the deliverable also examines EU-DREAM's interactions with other significant European initiatives and instruments, such as the Erasmus+ programme, Digital Innovation Hubs, the European Climate Pact, and the European Commission (EC) Digital Education Action Plan. The project is also actively seeking synergies with Horizon Europe instruments, including the European Research Council (ERC), Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), and the European Institute of Innovation and Technology's (EIT) Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs). While the primary focus of EU-DREAM's cooperation activities remains on BRIDGE and the E-ENERGY Cluster, additional actions are also being pursued. These efforts further strengthen the project's contribution to a holistic and integrated European approach to the digitalisation of the energy system. In doing so, they demonstrate how strategic collaboration is accelerating the transformation of the energy sector. Moreover, this approach is contributing to a more participatory and consumer-centric energy system in Europe, as shared learning and cooperation drive progress across the continent.

The information presented in this deliverable has been compiled using a variety of internal project management tools and documentation practices. Data sources include project tracking systems, minutes from internal and external meetings, event reports, participation records, and feedback from partners engaged in joint activities. This approach ensures a comprehensive and accurate representation of EU-DREAM's collaborative efforts throughout the reporting period.

In summary, this deliverable not only records the cooperation activities undertaken but also highlights their strategic value in amplifying project impact. The following sections provide a structured summary of cooperation activities across several domains, highlighting key actions, outcomes, and future directions.

Cooperation with Complementary EU projects: E-ENERGY cluster

The E-ENERGY cluster is an alliance of five Horizon Europe projects: EU-DREAM, ENERGENIUS, DIGITISE, DECODIT, and, most recently to join CELINE, each dedicated to empowering consumers through digital innovation in the energy sector. The cluster's vision is to democratise access to energy information, break down barriers to participation, and accelerate the energy transition by making digital energy services more understandable, accessible, and actionable for all Europeans. Inspired by the accessibility revolution of e-mails, the E-ENERGY cluster aims to create seamless experiences for energy consumers, making data and tools intuitive, fast, and empowering [2].

Since October 2024, the five projects that make up the E-ENERGY cluster have worked closely together, bringing the intensive collaboration of 85 partners. Through this partnership, the projects share knowledge, harmonise methodologies, and jointly advance consumer engagement, digital literacy, and active participation in energy markets. The E-ENERGY cluster serves as a dynamic platform for joint communication, coordinated outreach, and the co-development of shared tools that put consumers at the centre of the digital energy transition.

The remainder of this section presents the developed and planned activities for the E-ENERGY cluster, beginning with an overview of the participating projects and their distinct roles. This is followed by an explanation of how cluster meetings are coordinated to ensure effective collaboration. The next part provides insights into the creation of a shared branding and visual identity, reflecting the cluster's collective mission. This is complemented by a review of joint activities and key outputs, highlighting major events, publications, and outreach efforts to date. Finally, the section concludes with a forward-looking perspective on future cooperation ideas and opportunities to further strengthen collaboration among the member projects.

Participating Projects and Their Roles

1. EU-DREAM is focused on developing next-generation energy services and solutions that put the consumer first. The project leverages an AI-based assistant and an NLP intermediary to enable seamless, everyday language communication and optimise household energy settings. EU-DREAM's work is directly aligned with the broader cluster goal of empowering citizens and supporting easy, user-friendly access to energy and flexibility markets [1].

2. ENERGENIUS aggregates and harmonises cross-sectoral data from nine diverse domains, including energy, health, real estate, and social media. Using advanced AI, the project delivers personalised insights and practical tools via the

ENERGENIUS Suite. An engaging, serious game interface sustains citizen feedback and promotes ongoing involvement, enabling communities to benefit from tailored digital tools for energy management [4].

knowledge transfer [5].

3. DIGITISE aims to enhance digital literacy and empower consumers to actively engage with digital energy services and markets. The project's ambition is to ensure that both consumers and prosumers can participate meaningfully in the energy transition, with a focus on digital inclusion and

4. DECODIT is developing digital tools that enable citizens to make informed, sustainable energy choices. Its services include personalised propositions based on federated, data-driven insights and accessible natural language interfaces, along with innovative financing models designed to lower barriers to investment and participation [6].

5. CELINE aims to empower energy communities, households, and local groups by developing a user-friendly, harmonised digital framework for energy management and market participation. Through its Digital Toolbox, CELINE addresses barriers like limited market access and fragmented data, enabling communities to better produce, consume, and trade energy. The project supports the digitalisation and democratization of the energy sector, fostering more resilient and accessible energy systems across Europe [7].

Cluster Meetings and Coordination

Since its formation in late 2024, the E-ENERGY cluster has held regular online meetings, generally every six weeks, to coordinate joint activities and refine strategic objectives, focusing on:

- **Branding and Communication:** Developing a shared identity, cluster branding, and coordinated social media presence. Projects promote each other's activities via newsletters and digital channels, and share updates and resources for wider dissemination.
- **Planning Joint Activities:** Discussion and agreement on the organisation of joint webinars, workshops, and presence at major sector events (e.g., EU Sustainable Energy Week, Enlit, Sustainable Places, and Flexcon).
- **Collaborative Outputs:** Initiatives include an open letter addressing barriers to energy community growth, proposals for white papers and joint reviews, and the development of common outreach materials such as roll-ups, brochures, and podcasts.

Branding

The cluster's visual identity is not just a graphic element but a strategic tool to communicate its mission and vision to stakeholders across Europe. The design of the E-ENERGY logo (see Figure 1) encapsulates the cluster's core ambition: to make energy information dramatically more accessible to citizens through digital innovation. The stylized "E" serves as the focal point, symbolizing both digitalization and the transformative journey of information. The opposing arrows integrated into the logo reference the dynamic flow of information within the energy ecosystem, while the layered structure visually represents the complexity and depth of energy data, from everyday insights to advanced technical knowledge. The use of a magenta colour scheme communicates a high energy and a drive for innovation. Together, these elements result in a coherent and impactful identity that effectively communicates the cluster's commitment to making energy information accessible, actionable, and engaging for all.

Figure 1 – E-ENERGY cluster logo.

(a)

Figure 2 – E-ENERGY cluster mockups.

Joint Activities and Outputs

Key joint activities and outcomes from the E-ENERGY Cluster to date include:

- **Open Letter Initiative:** All cluster members are contributing to an open letter (to be published on Open Research Europe) highlighting persistent barriers to scaling energy communities in Europe, especially focusing on digital and AI-driven tools for citizen empowerment. The letter will consolidate experiences from all projects and propose practical solutions.
- **Joint Webinars and Workshops:** The cluster is organising its first joint webinar, with themes under consideration such as the use of AI in digital tools, citizen engagement strategies, and ethics in AI for energy communities. The goal is to broaden outreach, share best practices, and foster a more inclusive dialogue across the energy sector.
- **Presence at Major Events:** Cluster members coordinate joint representation and dissemination at flagship events, including EUSEW [8], Enlit [9], Sustainable Places [10], and Flexcon [11]. This includes shared booths, coordinated event materials, and cross-promotion of each project’s work, enhancing both visibility and impact.
- **Communication and Social Media Campaigns:** Regular coordination on social media, project newsletters, and shared communication resources to reach wider audiences, including the launch of a dedicated LinkedIn page and the sharing of news across channels.

- **Discussion of Joint Publications:** Plans for a joint white paper and possible peer-reviewed publications on citizen empowerment and digitalisation in the energy market, drawing on real-world pilot experiences.

Below, in Table 1, the upcoming and planned joint activities for the cluster are summarised.

Table 1 – Upcoming and Planned Joint Activities

Activity	Format	Cluster Partners Involved	Target Date	Status
<i>Open Letter</i>	Article	All	Feb 2026	Confirmed / In progress
<i>Joint Webinar</i>	Online event	All	To Be Defined	Confirmed / Topic voting stage
<i>EUSEW</i>	Conference	DECODIT, cluster representation	June 2025	Done
<i>Enlit</i>	Conference	All	Nov 2025	Confirmed
<i>Flexcon</i>	Conference	CELINE, cluster representation	Sep 2025	Planning
<i>Sustainable Places</i>	Conference	ENERGENIUS	Oct 2025	Confirmed
<i>White Paper</i>	Publication	All	End 2025	Concept phase

Cooperation Ideas and Outlook

Looking ahead, the E-ENERGY Cluster has identified several opportunities and ideas for deepening cooperation and amplifying impact:

- **Thematic Focus:** There is consensus to select a central theme for joint webinars and event participation, such as AI for digital tools, citizen engagement strategies, and overcoming adoption barriers, maximising coherence and outreach.
- **Resource Sharing:** Ongoing development of joint communication materials, including brochures and digital toolkits, to present a unified message at external events and online.
- **Event Collaboration:** Cluster members will continue to coordinate for joint booths, workshops, and panels at EU energy and digitalisation events, aiming for collective visibility and influence.
- **Content Creation:** Proposed joint podcast episodes and a series of webinars on ethics in AI, citizen empowerment, and market innovation for energy communities.
- **External Partnerships:** Outreach to additional projects (e.g., TwinEU [12]) to join or collaborate with the cluster, expanding expertise and broadening the network.
- **Joint Publications:** Moving forward with the open letter and exploring a white paper on digital empowerment and open digital services in the energy sector.

The E-ENERGY Cluster is still evolving, but its early results demonstrate the value of pooling expertise, aligning communication strategies, and co-creating resources for greater influence. This model of close cooperation is strengthening the ability of each project to accelerate consumer participation in the energy transition and is expected to set a benchmark for future digital energy initiatives in Europe.

Cooperation with the BRIDGE initiative

The BRIDGE initiative is an EC platform that unites projects funded under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe in the fields of smart grids, energy storage, islands, and digitalisation. Since its founding in 2016, BRIDGE has grown into a large and diverse community, now comprising over 200 projects and more than 2,000 partner organisations from across Europe. Its main purpose is to foster collaboration and structured dialogue among research and innovation projects to accelerate the clean and digital energy transition [13].

BRIDGE operates by promoting the exchange of information, practical experience, and lessons learned among its members. This collaborative environment enables projects to address shared technical and regulatory challenges, generate common solutions, and deliver coordinated recommendations to European policymakers. By leveraging real-world insights and concrete results from demonstration projects, BRIDGE helps to overcome the barriers to innovation and supports the effective deployment of new solutions within the energy sector.

To structure its activities, BRIDGE is organised around four dedicated Working Groups (WGs), each addressing a core area relevant to the digitalisation and transformation of the European energy system: Business Models, Regulation, Consumer and Citizen Engagement, and Data Management. They are described as follows [3].

- **Business Models** – aims at **defining a common language and frameworks around business model** description and valuation, identifying and evaluating existing and new or innovative business models from the project demonstrations or use cases [14]. The efforts of the Working Group are directed towards two specific areas of interest, namely:
 - The **design of tools to evaluate the benefit and values of the services and solutions** developed in the activities of the projects, including the investigation of the tools to capture business ideas and build the Business Model and the quantification methods for the Business Model's benefits of services and solutions under various Use Case scenarios.
 - **Designing a business model** that better incorporates the integration of the data value chain and the monetisation of data, where better observability creates additional social value.
- **Regulation** – focuses on **various regulatory aspects in the energy sector to identify best practices and provide recommendations** [15]. The Working group structures its activities addressing the regulatory challenges related to:
 - **Market access** by exploring the elements that need to be addressed and that would need further elaboration.
 - Peer to peer and **energy sharing**.
 - **Collective flexibility** to the grid in the context of overall market design, understanding the potential value of energy communities and peer to peer energy sharing.
 - **Sector coupling and integration**, addressing key barriers within the regulatory and market framework between various energy carriers and services across sectors to unlock synergies beneficial to consumers, market actors, and the overall system.

- **Market coordination and integration**, assisting system operators in grid preparation for 2030 by identifying how the absence of an integrated market hinders potential synergies in a more interconnected system, limiting the development potential of energy and flexibility services, markets, and platforms.
- **Consumer and Citizen Engagement** – focuses on creating a structured cross-cutting understanding of the **role and methodologies of citizen engagement in European R&I projects** towards triggering and leveraging the action of consumers and citizens in the energy landscape [16]. Building on this approach:
 - Focal points **are smart tools, indicators, and engagement strategies**.
 - **Consumers and citizens are crucial actors** to consider and engage when aiming to realize a just and sustainable energy transition in Europe – and beyond.
 - Technologies will only be accepted and taken up if **consumer needs are met and consumer concerns are mitigated**.
- **Data Management** – aims to cover a wide range of aspects, ranging from **the technical means for exchanging and processing data** between interested stakeholders to the **definition of rules** for exchange, including **security issues** and responsibility distribution in data handling [17]. The WG has identified three areas of collaboration:
 - **Data exchange framework** embracing the technical and non-technical aspects of the architecture needed to exchange data and the related requirements.
 - **Interoperability** promoting the adoption of common standards, protocols and sharing of use cases.
 - **Innovative technologies** that have the potential to impact data exchange and processing, including artificial intelligence.

Each WG is led by a chair and action leaders drawn from participating projects and is supported by a dedicated secretariat. This multi-stakeholder setup ensures that the diverse perspectives of research institutions, industry actors, consumers, regulators, and technology providers are all represented.

EU-DREAM plays an active role within BRIDGE, participating in all four Working Groups. The project brings expertise in artificial intelligence, digital twins, and natural language processing for energy management, contributing to discussions and actions on data federation, user-centric digital tools, and next-generation consumer engagement. By sharing the results and lessons from its Living Labs, AI-based assistant tools, and cross-sectoral data integration, EU-DREAM adds value to the ongoing collective work of the platform.

Engagement with BRIDGE also provides EU-DREAM with significant opportunities. The project benefits from networking with other leading European initiatives, accessing the latest knowledge on digitalisation trends, and aligning its outcomes with emerging best practices and policy recommendations. This cooperation enables EU-DREAM to amplify the impact of its solutions, gain greater visibility at the European level, and ensure that its innovations are relevant and scalable across diverse markets and regulatory contexts. The following sections provide a detailed account of EU-DREAM's participation, activities, and contributions within the BRIDGE initiative. Each of the four WGs is addressed individually, highlighting the project's specific roles, collaborative actions, added value, and lessons learned in each domain.

WG Business Model

EU-DREAM's involvement in the BRIDGE Business Model Working Group reflects a strategic commitment to advancing innovative and scalable business models for digital energy solutions. The project has actively participated in group discussions, knowledge exchanges, and surveys designed to identify best practices and standard methodologies for business model development across Horizon Europe projects.

A key contribution from EU-DREAM was the input provided to the BRIDGE-wide survey on business model development. The project emphasised the importance of establishing standardised key performance indicators (KPIs) sets that encompass not only economic outcomes, but also social and environmental impact. This approach ensures that future business models emerging from digital energy projects are robust, multidimensional, and aligned with the evolving requirements of policymakers and end-users. In addition, EU-DREAM contributed its perspective on the application of artificial intelligence for business model optimisation, drawing on its own research and use-case experiences in consumer-centric digital services.

By engaging in dialogue with other projects within the Business Model Working Group, particularly through partnerships with DEDALUS [18] and the broader Smart Energy Cluster initiative, EU-DREAM has greatly enriched its approach to business model innovation. DEDALUS contributes by developing practical tools that quantify the benefits of demand response, supporting the creation of viable and sustainable business cases. EU-DREAM has drawn on this perspective to strengthen its own methodology. At the same time, the Smart Energy Cluster unites more than 20 EU projects, creating an active ecosystem for the exchange of expertise, the merging of diverse energy services, and the inclusion of both energy and non-energy benefits. This collaborative and inclusive environment helps overcome market fragmentation and promotes cooperation, enabling participating projects to jointly develop approaches and speed up the adoption of innovative solutions and technologies.

Exposure to diverse experiences, such as those from OMEGA-X [19] and reviewing use cases from peers, has allowed EU-DREAM to integrate new strategies focused on scalability and replicability within its business models. Leveraging the collective knowledge and practical lessons developed within BRIDGE, the project has been able to continually refine its methodologies. This ongoing process ensures that EU-DREAM's business models remain robust, adaptable, and capable of delivering value across Europe's evolving energy sector.

WG Regulation

During its first year of involvement with the BRIDGE Regulation Working Group, EU-DREAM engaged in multiple actions and collaborative processes that sought to address regulatory challenges and foster greater integration of digital solutions into the energy sector. The working group operates through a series of targeted actions, each focusing on specific aspects of regulation, such as market access, energy sharing, flexibility market coordination, and sector integration. EU-DREAM's engagement is further strengthened by the leadership role of Helena Gerard, an EU-DREAM member from VITO research centre, who chairs the Regulation WG, ensuring that the project's perspective is present at the highest level of group coordination.

Among the WG's main activities, EU-DREAM contributed to Action 1: Improve Consumers' Market Access to Value Their Flexibility. While this action is still in its early phase, EU-DREAM is positioned to support discussions and share insights from its own research as project results mature. Active participation in WG's meetings enables EU-DREAM to stay aligned with the evolving regulatory discourse and to prepare for more substantial contributions as project outputs develop.

EU-DREAM's involvement in Action 2: Peer-to-Peer and Energy Sharing has been particularly tangible. Project partners provided country-specific input for Belgium (Flanders), ensuring this important region was represented in the knowledge base, as it had not yet been covered by other projects. The group's monthly meetings have become a platform for ongoing exchange, and EU-DREAM proposed a dedicated knowledge-sharing session on "Digital tools for energy sharing," recognising its particular significance for the project's commitment to digital innovation. Additionally, EU-DREAM participates in best practice discussions, with outcomes expected to inform both regulatory recommendations and the project's own use cases.

The project has also contributed to Action 3: Facilitate Energy and Flexibility Market Coordination and Integration by supplying information on Belgian legislation and engaging in early-stage presentations on the topic. As concrete evidence from EU-DREAM's case studies was still forthcoming at this stage, the project has laid the groundwork for deeper participation as its activities progress. Contributions to these actions ensure that the regulatory barriers and opportunities identified through EU-DREAM pilots are recognized at the European policy level.

For Action 4: Support the Potential Synergies from Increased Sector Coupling/Sector Integration/System Integration, EU-DREAM responded to surveys but was limited in its ability to provide concrete contributions due to the early stage of its use case development. Nevertheless, the project remains committed to supporting the group's objectives and anticipates a growing role as data and results from its living labs and pilots become available.

Beyond formal actions within BRIDGE, EU-DREAM has leveraged the expertise of its consortium partners, particularly VITO, whose team not only participates in but also leads several activities within the Regulation WG and related working groups, such as the International Smart Grid Action Network (ISGAN) [20]. This has enabled EU-DREAM to access additional international platforms, contribute to surveys on local flexibility markets, and share perspectives in discussions about explicit flexibility and sector integration, further broadening the project's impact and visibility.

WG Consumer and Citizen Engagement

EU-DREAM's engagement within the BRIDGE Consumer and Citizen Engagement Working Group has been marked by both active participation and leadership. The project has placed a particular emphasis on advancing strategies for inclusivity, the ethical use of AI in engagement, and the development of innovative methods and tools for effective stakeholder participation. A notable aspect of this engagement is the role of the EU-DREAM member Valeria Palladino, from ENEA, as co-leader of the "Strategies of Engagement" subgroup, strengthening both EU-DREAM's influence and the quality of the subgroup's activities.

One of the primary contributions was EU-DREAM's involvement in the design and completion of a comprehensive survey, focused on mapping the status and progress of stakeholder engagement across BRIDGE projects, with special attention to inclusivity and energy poverty, the integration of AI in engagement, and the effectiveness of various methodologies and tools. EU-DREAM provided detailed responses regarding its ongoing engagement activities, ensuring that the challenges and innovations of its living labs and community pilots were represented in the collective learning process.

In parallel, EU-DREAM took part in another survey dedicated to "smart tools" for engagement. Several project partners contributed insights into the methodologies and ethical frameworks guiding the project's smart tool development. These responses addressed key topics such as harmonisation strategies, user involvement, scalability, and security. This allowed EU-DREAM to share its emerging best practices and to identify shared challenges and recommendations with other projects across Europe.

Workshops made a substantial contribution to deepening knowledge exchange within the group. EU-DREAM took an active lead in organising and delivering two major workshops: one focused on AI and engagement, and another on inclusivity in stakeholder participation. The first workshop examined the many roles AI can play, from its integration in the EU-DREAM energy management system platform to its application in supporting engagement activities such as survey analysis and co-creation workshops. The project also contributed to discussions on the ethical implications of AI, highlighting the importance of transparency, quality control, and human oversight.

The workshop on inclusivity and engagement provided an opportunity to discuss how best to involve underserved and vulnerable groups in energy innovation. A key lesson highlighted during these sessions is that inclusion within research and innovation projects must be viewed as a strategic, long-term commitment, not as a one-time activity. Achieving meaningful participation demands early engagement, co-design, and ongoing trust-building, while simultaneously addressing challenges related to affordability, digital access, and societal mistrust. Moreover, creating a genuinely inclusive energy transition goes beyond the efforts of individual projects; it also depends on systemic support, including effective policies, sufficient funding, and sustained institutional commitment.

EU-DREAM's visibility in the broader BRIDGE community was further enhanced at the BRIDGE General Assembly in Brussels (March 2025). Represented by Valeria Palladino and Gianluca Lipari, EU-DREAM was showcased among new projects in the "Networking Coffee & New Projects Showcase" session (see Figure 3) [21]. This opportunity allowed the project to highlight its expected outcomes and build connections with fellow initiatives working on consumer and citizen engagement throughout Europe.

Figure 3 - EU-DREAM representation in the New Projects Showcase at the BRIDGE General Assembly.

Beyond these activities, EU-DREAM has contributed to the annual report of the Consumer and Citizen Engagement WG, with particular mention of its strategies and upcoming work on AI-supported engagement. The project’s methodologies and anticipated results have become reference points within the working group, reflecting a growing recognition of EU-DREAM’s innovative and ethical approach.

Participation in this working group has also provided EU-DREAM with critical lessons. The project has learned that AI presents powerful opportunities to enhance stakeholder engagement, streamline communication, and support research activities, yet its adoption must be handled with care. Rather than serving as a replacement for human interaction, AI should act as a supportive partner, guided by strong ethical standards, robust quality assurance, and transparency regarding its application. However, the need for new frameworks and metrics to evaluate the real impact of AI on stakeholder involvement remains an open challenge. Moreover, achieving true inclusivity demands a sustained and coordinated effort, both within individual projects and at the systemic level, through supportive policies and funding.

WG Data Management

EU-DREAM has demonstrated active engagement within the BRIDGE Data Management Working Group, recognising that robust and interoperable data practices are critical to the digital transformation of Europe's energy landscape. The project contributed to a series of collaborative surveys and knowledge-sharing initiatives focused on standards, interoperability, and the role of artificial intelligence in data management. EU-DREAM partners played a central role in responding to key surveys, such as the "Interoperability of Home Appliances" and the "Reference Framework Survey on Use of Standards", ensuring that project experience and technical insights fed directly into the collective work of the WG.

A significant focus for EU-DREAM in this WG was on understanding and harmonising the use of AI within the energy sector. EU-DREAM provided feedback on the draft "Survey on the Usage of AI in the Energy Sector", especially mobilising Living Lab partners to participate and disseminate the survey. This cross-partner approach ensured that a diverse range of practical, real-world insights from different national contexts and energy use cases were captured, enriching the survey's relevance and value to the entire BRIDGE community.

Participation in the Data Management WG meetings and surveys also allowed EU-DREAM to exchange feedback with a broad array of projects, facilitating an environment of mutual learning and alignment. The project found a strong convergence with key findings, particularly regarding the importance of using standardised protocols and reference frameworks, such as the IEC 62559-2 [22] for use case structuring and DERA 3.0 [23] for data architecture. These tools offer EU-DREAM ready-made templates and methodologies to streamline its own use case development, supporting interoperability and plug-and-play solutions within and beyond the project.

Lessons learned through the WG's activities have underscored the importance of standardized data exchange and the practical value of generic business processes (GBPs). These GBPs serve as reusable templates for key energy data interactions, such as flexibility activation and meter data exchange, making it more efficient to design, implement, and test services in alignment with practices adopted by other EU projects. Additionally, EU-DREAM has benefited from collective contributions to established standards, including widely used data models, communication protocols, and open-source implementations. Leveraging these resources reduces the need for custom integrations and ensures that project solutions remain compatible with European best practices.

Cooperation with Other EU Initiatives/Instruments

Beyond its central engagement with complementary Horizon Europe projects and the BRIDGE initiative, EU-DREAM is committed to building meaningful cooperation with a wide array of other EU initiatives and instruments. These include cross-sectoral programmes and networks that foster innovation, digitalisation, and citizen engagement throughout Europe's energy transition.

One strategic opportunity for collaboration is the Erasmus+ programme, which supports education, training, youth, and sport across Europe. EU-DREAM explores synergies with Erasmus+ projects to promote digital skills, lifelong learning, and capacity building relevant to the energy sector. Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) represent another valuable partner network, as they foster digital transformation and support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), startups, and public institutions in adopting advanced digital solutions for energy management, flexibility services, and market participation.

The project also seeks alignment with broader policy-driven initiatives such as the European Climate Pact, which mobilises citizens, communities, and organisations to take concrete climate and sustainability action, and the European Commission Digital Education Action Plan, which aims to enhance digital literacy and education for all European citizens. Through these linkages, EU-DREAM not only benefits from a rich ecosystem of resources and expertise but also contributes to shaping a more inclusive and digitally skilled energy society.

Additionally, EU-DREAM is actively seeking synergies with flagship Horizon Europe instruments, including the European Research Council (ERC), Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA), and the European Institute of Innovation and Technology's (EIT) Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs). These instruments offer opportunities for high-level research collaboration, talent development, and technology transfer, which are essential elements for scaling up innovation and ensuring the sustainability of project outcomes across the EU.

By engaging with this diverse portfolio of EU initiatives and instruments, EU-DREAM is well-positioned to amplify the impact of its digital solutions, foster interdisciplinary collaboration, and contribute to capacity building and knowledge exchange across sectors. These partnerships open pathways for mutual learning, support the dissemination of best practices, and enhance the overall resilience and digital maturity of Europe's energy system.

The following sections provide a detailed account of EU-DREAM's participation, activities, and contributions within these various EU initiatives and instruments, highlighting specific collaborative actions and anticipated future opportunities.

Erasmus+ Program

Within the context of the Erasmus+ programme [24], EU-DREAM, through both individual and coordinated actions by its partners, is well-positioned to contribute to key priorities such as digital transformation, the green transition, and inclusive education.

The project's tools, platforms, and methodologies developed across various work packages can support the advancement of digital skills, promote sustainable energy practices, and foster social inclusion, as described next.

1. Development of Digital Educational Content for Energy Literacy

- **Create modular digital learning resources** on key topics such as energy consumption, flexibility services, smart grid technologies, and citizen participation in energy markets.
- These resources can be integrated into Erasmus+ **higher education** and **vocational education and training (VET)** programs focused on sustainability, energy engineering, environmental studies, and Information and Communication Technology.
- The learning materials will be designed to accommodate diverse learning levels, from introductory (for non-experts) to advanced (for technical experts).

2. Development of Advanced Educational Resources

- Research outcomes from UCLM's agent-based modelling (ABM) framework could be translated into **specialized case studies and training materials** for different educational levels. Contributions could include:
 - For Higher Education (Master/PhD): Modules on "**Comparative Analysis of Business Models** for Local Energy Markets" and "**Consumer Acceptance Factors for AI in Energy Systems**".
 - For Professionals: Executive summaries and case studies focused on the **practical implications of consumer behaviour** for energy companies and policymakers, highlighting the need for transdisciplinary collaboration between engineers, social scientists, and designers to achieve successful innovation.
- Leverage the partner's unique research expertise to train the next generation of **socio-technical energy modelers**. Contributions could include:
 - Hosting international **PhD students** for short-term research stays (Erasmus+ Mobility) to work on specific **modelling challenges**.
 - Co-supervising Master's Theses that focus on applying **agent-based modelling to new energy community scenarios**.

3. Integration into Blended and Online Learning Formats

- The digital platform developed in EU-DREAM's work package (WP) 4 – "Digital Platforms, Tools and Technologies for Energy Services", includes **interactive visualisation tools**, **AI-supported user guidance**, and **personalised information modules**. These can be adapted into **virtual labs**, simulations, and real-world data exercises to be used in Erasmus+ blended learning courses.
- **Strategic Partnerships** under Erasmus+ can be established to co-develop cross-institutional digital training environments using the platform's components.

4. Promotion of Digital Skills and Competencies in the Energy Sector

- **Micro-credential programs** or **short courses** can be implemented targeting energy-related digital skills (e.g., understanding energy bills, participating in digital energy marketplaces, interpreting consumption data).

- **Digital Opportunity Traineeships** can be offered, providing practical internships focused on energy software development, UI/UX testing, and data integration.

5. Lifelong Learning and Adult Education Initiatives

- Partnerships with local authorities, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and educational providers can be established to use the WP4 platform for **community-based training workshops** on energy awareness and digital participation, especially targeting low-skilled or older adults.
 - This supports Erasmus+ objectives for **social inclusion, active citizenship, and climate action education**.

6. Teacher and Staff Training

- **Training modules for educators and trainers** can be offered, focused on how to use the WP4 platform to **teach energy market topics** in digitally enhanced ways.
 - This includes guidance on integrating platform functionalities into lesson plans, using analytics to track student progress, and adapting content for different learner profiles.
- Offer **training sessions** for researchers and educators on the topics of **AI for energy systems**.
 - An **Erasmus+ mobility is already scheduled** for September/2025 to send a researcher from the University of Porto to Aalborg University for a one-week knowledge exchange focused on data collection, curation, and analysis for AI-based energy consumption forecasting.
- Provide **ongoing mentoring**, enabling trainers to continuously refine their digital-energy teaching methods.

7. AI and Energy Educational Modules

- Create modular digital learning resources on key topics related to energy systems and AI, designed for both non-expert audiences and advanced technical users.

8. Community-Based Digital Energy Workshops

- Partner with local NGOs, adult education centres and youth organisations to deliver outreach workshops where participants explore simple AI-driven applications in the energy context.
- Tailor content to promote social inclusion and climate awareness.

9. Support for Evidence-Based Community and Policy Making

- **Share the actionable insights from UCLM's ABM framework** with non-academic stakeholders to support inclusive and effective decision-making. Contributions could include:
 - Providing local authorities and energy cooperatives with analysis on key adoption barriers (e.g., trust, aversion to control) to help them **design more effective citizen engagement strategies**.

- Offering insights on how different incentive structures or policy scenarios could impact the adoption rates and economic viability, allowing for a better alignment of consumer, energy, and environmental policies to reinforce sustainable demand.
- Providing simulation-based analysis of how digital tools and services might perform in diverse geographic and socio-economic contexts.

10. Curriculum Development Using Digital Twin Technologies (KA2 – Partnerships for Innovation)

- Co-develop transdisciplinary educational modules incorporating digital twin frameworks for real-time modelling and optimization of integrated energy systems.
- Integrate AI, IoT, and simulation-based control methods into higher education curricula to train students in data-centric energy system design and operation.
- Facilitate the transfer of research outputs from EU-DREAM **WP2** – “Digital Twin, AI-based Assistant Tool and NLP-based Intermediator” into open-access learning tools and modular teaching packages for use across European institutions.

11. Living Labs as Real-World Learning Infrastructures (KA2 – Alliances for Education and Enterprises)

- Utilize living labs of **WP7** – “Living Labs, SSH Intertwining, Replicability and Business Innovation” as experiential learning environments where learners engage with real-world socio-technical data, behavioural modelling, and participatory system design.
- Enable collaboration between academia, municipalities, and industry to co-create energy transition solutions that are both technically viable and socially inclusive.
- Support the development of new pedagogical approaches rooted in living lab methodology and problem-based learning, targeting upskilling and reskilling across professional and academic sectors.

12. Policy Support and Digital Capacity Building (KA3 – Support to Policy Development and Cooperation)

- Provide evidence-based recommendations for educational policy and digital skills strategies based on insights from WP2 and WP7.
- Contribution to national and EU-level dialogues on the integration of digital twin technologies in education and workforce training for the green transition.
- Offer technical training sessions, policy briefs, and open-access datasets to support institutional digital readiness in line with the Digital Education Action Plan.

Digital Innovation Hubs

Some EU-DREAM partners possess unique expertise and connections with Digital Innovation Hubs, enabling them to make targeted contributions in this area. These specific strengths allow the project to support digital transformation in the energy sector through tailored actions and collaborations.

AUTH is responsible for designing and testing a modular and open digital platform architecture capable of supporting AI-powered services and personalised user interaction within energy systems. It focuses on providing a flexible, extensible software environment that can host third-party algorithms, models, and user services — fully aligned with the needs and structure of DIHs. ENEA demonstrates a similar alignment through its activities in the EU-DREAM project, its expertise in AI and energy systems, and the availability of advanced laboratories in areas such as power systems, hydrogen, power converters, and thermal microgrids. AAU contributes by developing next-generation digital energy tools, such as digital twin models and AI-based control systems designed for smart energy applications. Its IoT-MG Lab serves as a living lab and testbed for advanced microgrid integration and human-centric energy solutions, positioning AAU as a strong collaborator for DIHs focused on strengthening digital capabilities in the clean energy transition. Furthermore, beyond its academic contributions, UCLM's research within EU-DREAM is designed to generate practical insights for the energy industry. Their work on business models and consumer behaviour analysis positions them as a strategic partner for DIHs. Thus, the EU-DREAM can provide the following opportunities.

1. Provision of a Modular Platform Architecture for DIH Deployment

- The WP4 platform provides a **containerised and open deployment environment** that DIHs can use to:
 - Deploy custom AI/ML models for energy forecasting, demand prediction, or user behaviour modelling.
 - Integrate local or regional datasets into the platform through defined APIs and data ingestion modules.
 - Adapt interfaces and user journeys for local use cases (e.g., SMEs, municipalities, energy cooperatives).
- The platform is offered as a **reference architecture** for DIHs working on digital energy services, with guidance on how to deploy, test, and adapt AI models in their regional context.

2. Technical Collaboration on AI Deployment and Data Integration

- AUTH and ENEA can support DIHs in:
 - Deploying their own experimental models, also, where possible, within the platform designed in WP4 (e.g., for smart grid services, energy efficiency advisory).
 - Integrating heterogeneous datasets from public administrations, energy providers, or end users into the platform using its flexible data layer.
 - Provide technical assistance and documentation to DIHs wishing to experiment with AI deployment within a scalable, modular platform framework.

3. Bridging AI, Microgrids, and Digital Twin Technologies for DIH Collaboration

- AAU's simulation environments and AI tools allow DIHs to:
 - Integrate real-time data streams from diverse energy assets into digital twin platforms.

- Prototype smart grid solutions within microgrid-scale testbeds at LL6, including distributed storage, power electronics, and demand-side control.

4. Enabling Co-Development and Experimentation with SMEs

- DIHs often work with SMEs lacking the infrastructure to test AI algorithms in realistic settings. The platform, designed to support **external model execution**, offers:
 - A **live experimentation environment** for testing SME-developed components under simulated user conditions.
 - Access to **evaluation protocols** for usability, performance, and user interaction.
- **Sandbox pilots or prototyping sprints** can be co-organised in collaboration with DIHs and local SMEs, using the WP4 platform as a shared base.
- The AAU's IoT-MG Lab provides an applied innovation space where SMEs can:
 - Collaboratively test energy solutions in a controlled yet realistic microgrid environment.
 - Access AAU's domain expertise in resilient distributed energy systems, IoT integration, and user-centred AI design.
 - Engage in iterative co-development cycles with researchers and community stakeholders.

5. Supporting DIH Training and Technical Demonstration

- The open WP4 platform and the research centre laboratories can serve as a training environment for DIHs to:
 - Demonstrate AI-driven user interaction, explainability, and decision support in energy contexts.
 - Educate regional actors (startups, utilities, public entities) on **how AI models are operationalised in scalable infrastructures**.
- **Technical workshops or webinars** can be delivered for DIH staff and external stakeholders using WP4 platform deployments and simulated data, and insights from other WPs and living labs.
- AAU supports DIHs by hosting:
 - **Hands-on training workshops** and technical demonstrations on AI in energy systems, digital twin deployment, and data-driven microgrid control.
 - Tailored support for DIHs to replicate digital twin frameworks and scale digitalization strategies across regional energy networks.

6. Contribution to EU-Wide DIH Networks and Toolkits

- AUTH can contribute its experience in modular energy platform design to:
 - **EU-level DIH knowledge exchanges**, offering architectural blueprints and open APIs.
 - **Provide best practices** for AI deployment and digital energy ecosystems.

- AUTH can participate in **coordinated actions** and DIH clusters as a technical partner, contributing validated platform designs for real-world applications.

7. Strategic Analysis and Market De-risking

- **Simulation-based analysis** can be provided to help companies make informed strategic decisions before investing in product development.
 - Evaluate the market viability and potential adoption rates of new energy services.
 - Identify key behavioural barriers to product adoption, such as lack of trust in AI, aversion to control, or perceived complexity.
 - 'Stress-test' business models against different community profiles (e.g., sceptical vs. tech-savvy consumers) to identify weaknesses.

8. Support for User-Centric Product Design

- Applying **insights from behavioural research** to help companies design products that consumers will not only need but also want to use.
 - Analyse the effectiveness of different incentive structures and pricing schemes for various consumer profiles.
 - Define evidence-based user profiles (archetypes) that help companies better understand their target customers.
 - Conduct strategic co-design workshops where simulation results are used to refine and improve a company's value proposition.

9. Knowledge Transfer and Capacity Building

- Transferring specialized knowledge to strengthen the capabilities of the DIH ecosystem.
 - **Specialized seminars** for SMEs on topics such as "**Integrating Behavioural Science into Tech Innovation**" or "**Methodologies for Energy Market Validation**".
 - Academic collaboration through the co-supervision of Master's Theses and hosting researchers for short-term stays

10. Analysis of Human-Centric Digital Platforms

- Providing **analysis of the psychosocial and behavioural factors** that drive the adoption and use of digital energy platforms.
 - Develop socio-demographic and psychosocial segmentation of energy consumers for a specific region or market.
 - Analyse key drivers of energy choices, such as trust, risk perception, social norms, and the impact of behavioural economics principles.
 - Provide **recommendations for inclusive design** to ensure digital platforms are accessible and effective for all demographics.

11. Evaluation of Demand Activation and Flexibility through Digital Means

- Using UCLM's simulation framework to **evaluate the effectiveness of digital services** designed to activate and shape consumer demand for grid support.

- Assess the effectiveness of personalized energy feedback and adaptive tariff models.
- Conduct scenario testing to analyse the potential of community-based demand aggregation to enhance grid resilience and renewable integration.
- Provide analysis on the interoperability challenges from a consumer adoption perspective, identifying potential friction points.

12. Social Innovation and New Market Roles for Consumers & Interoperability Standards

- Exploring the **socio-economic impacts of new market roles** for consumers enabled by digitalization.
 - Analyse the emergence of local energy markets and the new economic roles for consumers as prosumers, aggregators, or data providers.
 - Provide **simulation-based impact assessments** on how these new models could affect local development, energy poverty, or employment.
 - Develop **econometric-informed agent-based models** for Peer-to-Peer (P2P) trading and collective self-consumption.

European Climate Pact

The European Climate Pact [25] is a flagship initiative under the European Green Deal, launched by the European Commission to engage citizens, communities, and organisations in the transition to a climate-neutral Europe by 2050. EU-DREAM supports these objectives through the development of digital platforms, educational tools, and research activities that foster climate awareness and drive behavioural change. By equipping individuals and communities with practical resources and knowledge, the project empowers a broader range of actors to take meaningful climate action at the local level. These coordinated efforts help advance the core pillars of the Pact, promoting inclusiveness, supporting local initiatives, and contributing to Europe's collective journey toward climate neutrality. The following activities, initiatives, and actions illustrate EU-DREAM's concrete contributions in this context.

Strategic Contribution Areas and Recommended Actions

1. Climate Awareness through Quantitative Analysis and Energy Transparency

The project research will produce quantitative analyses that translate consumer energy decisions into environmental outcomes. Also, the WP4 platform offers tools that allow users to:

- Visualise and monitor their energy consumption.
- Understand the environmental and carbon impact of their choices.
- Receive AI-generated suggestions for energy-saving behaviours.

Actions:

- Publish the results from UCLM’s ABM framework that quantify how different business models impact key metrics such as local renewable energy self-consumption and reduced grid dependency.
- Generate simulation-based case studies that serve as reference material to demonstrate the potential impact of collective actions, including the development of metrics that balance economic, social, and environmental outcomes.
- Develop and publicly release a "**Climate Impact Mode**" in the platform interface that explicitly translates energy usage into emissions and environmental indicators.
- Include **explanatory narratives** and contextual prompts aligned with Climate Pact messaging, e.g., "This week your home emitted X kg of CO₂."

2. Supporting Individual and Community-Level Climate Action

The European Climate Pact promotes citizen empowerment, cooperation and local initiative development. The EU-DREAM analysis of business models identifies the incentive structures and market conditions that are most effective in fostering cooperation, particularly in dynamic flexibility markets. Furthermore, the outcomes in EU-DREAM’s WP6 – “Energy Literacy Empowerment” can:

- Help users set **personal energy goals** (e.g., reducing heating, increasing efficiency).
- Facilitate **community-wide campaigns** or challenges using shared metrics and gamified platforms.
- Link users with local climate groups, energy cooperatives, or sustainability networks.

Actions:

- Develop and publish a methodology for the socio-technical viability assessment of local energy initiatives.
- Provide scenario analyses comparing the effectiveness of different approaches (e.g., markets vs. central aggregation) in achieving community-level objectives, including specific recommendations on economic incentives for households to participate in Demand Side Response (DSR).
- Design a web platform or mobile app to enable users to commit to energy-related climate actions and track their progress.
- Develop a **public dashboard** that aggregates anonymised community data to highlight collective climate achievements.
- Provide guidance, practical frameworks, and best practices for responsibly implementing AI-driven digital tools in energy management, highlighting both opportunities and potential risks (such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and transparency issues) to promote ethical, inclusive, and trustworthy deployment of AI technologies in climate action.

3. Inclusion and Accessibility

A central goal of the European Climate Pact is to engage all segments of society, including those with limited digital or technical skills.

- WP6 focuses on co-creating tools that are understandable and usable for non-experts.

Actions:

- Partner with **municipalities, schools, and NGOs** to roll out the tools in workshops targeting seniors, youth, and underserved groups.
- Publish a detailed analysis of adoption barriers for digital energy services, including lack of trust in AI, aversion to control, and perceived complexity.
- Segment these findings by consumer archetypes to inform which groups may require greater support or different service designs, ensuring social equity is considered in policy recommendations.

4. Climate Education and Citizen Empowerment

The European Climate Pact calls for widespread climate education and a stronger sense of agency among citizens.

- WP6 supports learning-by-doing through interactive interfaces.

Actions:

- Package a version of the platform as a "**Climate Education Toolkit**" for secondary schools, technical institutes, and adult training programs.
- Develop accessible digital educational materials focused on AI applications in the energy context, designed for schools, training centres, and community education platforms, to enhance climate literacy and promote informed behavioural changes.
- Facilitate community-driven AI-energy workshops in partnership with local municipalities, NGOs, and educational centres, enabling participants to explore simple, practical AI-supported energy solutions.
- Collaborate with Erasmus+ and Digital Education Action Plan initiatives to integrate these resources into pan-European education efforts.

5. Institutional Engagement and Climate Pact Participation

Several EU-DREAM partners can go beyond technical contributions by actively participating in the European Climate Pact as an organisation.

Actions:

- Nominate staff as **Climate Pact Ambassadors**, showcasing WP4 platform and WP6 tools in national and EU-level events.
- Contribute to **Pact's best practices**, toolkits, and public campaigns by sharing lessons learned and methodologies.

6. Enhancing Climate Literacy with AI and Digital Twins

EU-DREAM develops transparent, accessible tools that raise climate awareness and promote informed behavioural change.

- Provides real-time feedback on energy consumption through digital twin models and user-friendly dashboards.
- Utilises NLP to make complex energy and climate data understandable to all users, regardless of technical expertise.
- Implements “**Climate Impact Advisor**” features that explain the environmental consequences of consumption in plain language.
- Offers customizable dashboards that convert sensor data into personal emissions profiles and localized climate indicators.

Actions:

- Integrate AI-driven transparency tools into community outreach and education efforts to strengthen climate literacy at scale.

7. Driving Local Action and Community Engagement through Living Labs

The project’s Living Labs create participatory, real-world environments where climate solutions are co-designed with citizens and stakeholders.

- Facilitates experimentation with neighbourhood-scale interventions and peer-learning models.
- Encourages collective behaviour change via shared climate metrics and AI-powered feedback loops.
- Launches participatory “Energy Citizenship Challenges,” using digital twin data to monitor local progress on climate goals.
- Connects with municipal platforms for joint tracking of emissions trends and climate actions.

Actions:

- Expand living lab approaches to more regions, enabling more communities to co-create and adopt climate solutions using EU-DREAM’s methodologies.

European Commission Digital Education Action Plan

EU-DREAM is actively advancing the priorities of the EU’s Digital Education Action Plan [26] by developing digital platforms, innovative interfaces, and effective pedagogical tools that enhance energy literacy and digital skills. Through coordinated research and the creation of adaptable educational methodologies, the project supports the production of high-quality digital learning content and strengthens capacity-building efforts in the energy sector. These initiatives contribute to equipping learners and professionals with the skills needed to thrive in a digitally transformed, sustainable energy landscape. The key strategic priorities addressed by these actions are described in the following.

Priority 1: Fostering the Development of a High-Performing Digital Education Ecosystem

- **Adapt WP4 platform features** into structured educational content for use in secondary schools, vocational training, and higher education.
- Develop a "**Digital Learning Mode**" within the platform, offering structured micro-lessons, quizzes, and certifications related to energy and sustainability.
- Collaborate with universities, schools, and adult learning centres to **pilot the WP4 platform** as a tool for teaching digital energy literacy.
- Supply high-level guidelines and illustrative energy sector case studies on responsible AI in the energy context.
- Feed into the Commission's structured dialogue and Council recommendations on enabling factors and blended learning approaches.
- Co-design modular digital education units on digital twin models and AI for energy topics.
- Publish UCLM's ABM framework and simulation results as Open Educational Resources (OERs), which can be used by higher education instructors to create their own teaching materials.
- Teach how to use simulation concepts of behavioural economics in the energy community context.
- Prepare an online seminar for researchers.

Priority 2: Enhancing energy digital skills and competences for the digital age

- Create **short digital learning modules as part of WP6** that address basic to advanced digital energy skills (e.g., reading energy data, using AI assistants, understanding smart meters).
- Offer these modules as part of **open educational resources (OERs)**, suitable for integration into Erasmus+, teacher training, or lifelong learning programs.
- Design and disseminate **inclusive digital materials** that support learners from underserved communities (e.g., simplified interfaces, multilingual content, mobile-first layouts).
- Developing common guidelines for educators to integrate basic AI/energy literacy and tackle misinformation in energy contexts.
- Hosting trainees at research centres to apply their digital, energy and AI skills on real datasets, bridging education.
- Publish research findings that identify the critical digital energy skills required for market participation, such as interpreting price signals and understanding the value of flexibility.
- Through Open Access publications, we disseminate the project research, ensuring our analyses are written with a focus on clarity and applicability. Our findings on how different consumer profiles interact with digital tools will provide an evidence base for educators and trainers to develop their own inclusive learning materials tailored to their specific needs.

European Research Council

EU-DREAM brings together several partners with strong research backgrounds and complementary expertise, positioning the consortium as a potential contributor to future ERC proposals. Building on their experience within EU-DREAM, these partners are well prepared to advance innovative research initiatives aligned with ERC priorities.

AUTH's research in WP4 and WP6 of EU-DREAM lays the scientific and technical groundwork for future ERC proposals by contributing to:

- Theoretical advancement in user-centric energy systems and AI-driven energy interaction.
- Experimental digital infrastructures to test human-AI interfaces in energy contexts.
- Methodologies for data-driven, personalised guidance in complex socio-technical environments.

The development of **open, modular digital platforms** that combine **AI models, natural language interfaces**, and **personalised decision-making** in the energy sector raises deep, **unexplored scientific questions**, such as:

- How can digital platforms mediate citizen interaction with complex systems like the energy grid?
- What are the cognitive effects of AI-guided decision-making in sustainability behaviours?
- How can personalisation algorithms balance automation with user agency in energy choices?

These are **theoretical and empirical questions** of high scientific interest, suitable for ERC domains in:

- Computer Science and Informatics
- Human Behaviour and Social Systems
- Systems and Communication Engineering
- Energy Systems and Environmental Engineering

Potential research challenges

- AI-human interaction for sustainability,
- Cognitive decision systems in socio-technical platforms,
- Behavioural digital infrastructure design.

➤ **Leverage WP4 Energy Marketplace Digital Platform to define a novel ERC project.** The platform's capacity to **mediate between human cognition and algorithmic decision models** in energy marketplaces can form the basis for such a proposal.

Possible proposals:

- Decision-making under algorithmic advice: **How do users respond when AI tools offer strategies based on price forecasts or consumption profiles?**
- Transparency and trust in AI: **What makes users trust (or reject) AI-generated suggestions in energy markets where money, risk, and sustainability are involved?**
- Feedback loop modelling: **How do repeated interactions with the platform alter user behaviour, preferences, or understanding of energy systems?**

ENEA is also well-positioned to support and enhance the objectives of the ERC, particularly regarding frontier research and innovation. Possible contributions include:

- Supporting Frontier AI-Energy Research
 - Providing access to curated datasets, scenarios, and AI models developed in energy contexts that can serve as foundational resources for ERC-funded frontier research, enabling researchers to address complex interdisciplinary challenges at the intersection of AI, energy transition, and climate change.
- Enabling Methodological Innovation in AI and Energy
 - Offering methodological guidance, expertise, and best practices on AI techniques specifically tailored to energy systems, thereby helping ERC-funded projects integrate cutting-edge AI methodologies in rigorous and reproducible ways.
- Capacity Building and Knowledge Exchange
 - Facilitating or co-organizing scientific workshops, seminars, and networking events that bring together ERC-funded researchers, AI specialists, and energy-sector stakeholders, fostering exchanges on emerging research trends, technological innovations, and cross-sectoral applications in energy systems and climate action.

UCLM's research in the EU-DREAM project also lays the scientific and methodological groundwork for future high-impact ERC proposals. Their work moves beyond purely techno-economic analysis to explore the complex socio-technical dynamics of the energy transition, generating foundational knowledge for frontier research. Their future contributions could be focused on the following areas:

- Advancing the Theory of Socio-Technical Energy Systems
 - Developing a theory of hybrid human-AI decision-making that models the co-evolution of user trust and algorithmic performance.
 - Investigating the emergence of social norms (e.g., cooperation, fairness) within digital energy markets and their impact on overall system efficiency and resilience.

- Providing Methodologies for Complex Systems Analysis
 - Identifying "tipping points" and non-linear dynamics in community energy systems, exploring how the composition of consumer profiles can determine the success or failure of new business models.
 - Modelling the resilience of energy communities not only to technical failures but also to behavioural shocks, such as a crisis of trust or the spread of misinformation.
- Posing New, High-Impact Scientific Questions
 - The current research opens deep and unexplored scientific questions suitable for the evaluation domains of the ERC, such as:
 - Physical Sciences and Engineering (PE): PE7 (Electrical, Systems, Modelling and Simulation Engineering) and PE8 (Energy, Products and Processes Engineering).
 - Social Sciences and Humanities (SH): SH1 (Individuals, Markets and Organisations) and SH3 (The Social World and its Dynamics).

AAU's development of **digital twin infrastructures and AI-driven optimization tools** (WP2) provides a robust foundation for ERC researchers exploring the convergence of energy systems and intelligent technologies. These platforms can serve as open, testable environments for advancing novel hypotheses in areas such as predictive control, adaptive systems, and human-machine energy interaction. Thus, possible contributions include:

- Catalysing Methodological Advances
 - Beyond technical outputs, AAU contributes to methodological innovation through:
 - Experimentation with multi-domain co-simulation techniques in digital twins.
 - Application of explainable AI to energy system planning.
 - Such innovations offer high potential for replication, extension, and integration in ERC-funded research spanning engineering, computer science, and environmental studies.
- Enabling a Research-Driven Ecosystem through Living Labs
 - The living labs coordinated in WP7 provide ERC researchers with direct access to real-world socio-technical environments where energy solutions are tested collaboratively with citizens, municipalities, and industry partners. This enables:
 - Cross-disciplinary field studies.
 - Validation of models in live conditions.
 - Embedding of societal relevance in technical research agendas.

- Fostering Talent, Networks, and Scientific Dialogue
 - AAU actively supports knowledge exchange by organizing doctoral schools, thematic workshops, and scientific symposia focused on the intersections of AI, energy, and climate systems. Its open infrastructure, combined with ERC collaboration, can enhance the visibility and impact of frontier research across Europe and beyond.

Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

EU-DREAM, through the combined expertise and collaboration of its partners, is well-positioned to contribute to the objectives of the MSCA. The project's strong foundation in digital innovation, energy systems modelling, and advanced research methods creates a supportive environment for fostering researcher mobility, interdisciplinary exchange, and high-quality scientific training. By leveraging this collaborative network, EU-DREAM can facilitate knowledge transfer and career development for early-stage and experienced researchers, fully aligning with the goals of the MSCA programme.

1. Postdoctoral Fellowships (PF)

For individual researchers (EU or global) to carry out **a research project** at a research centre associated with EU-DREAM, building on or expanding the project's themes.

Advantages:

- Hosts an advanced experimental digital platform in energy markets.
- Provides real-world validation and participatory testing opportunities in living labs, bridging technical research with socio-technical insights.
- Offers research placements and mentorship in AI, digital systems, and socio-technical interface design.
- Delivers advanced interdisciplinary training in hybrid energy simulation, digital twins, and AI optimization, supporting skill-building across engineering, computing, and climate sciences.

What should be done:

- Define high-impact Postdoctoral Fellowships topics, such as:
 - AI-guided behavioural adaptation in decentralised energy markets.
 - Energy literacy and gamification in digital platforms.
 - Operation strategies in electricity markets.
 - Market-clearing procedures.
 - Pricing of energy and security.
 - Advanced digital twin models for multi-energy systems.
 - Other cutting-edge topics such as AI-driven energy solutions, optimization algorithms, etc.
- Recruit early-career researchers and help them shape Postdoctoral Fellowships proposals hosted by a research centre associated with EU-DREAM.

2. Doctoral Networks (DN)

Multi-partner doctoral training programs combining academic and industrial supervision.

EU-DREAM's advantage:

- Can lead or participate in DNs focusing on:
 - Digital energy services,
 - AI in human-machine systems,
 - Human-centric platform design for sustainability.
 - AI-for-energy in green and digital transitions.
 - Consumer behaviour and user-centric business model.

What should be done:

- Develop a **Doctoral Network concept** aligned with project research topics.
- Partner with:
 - Tech companies (e.g., energy platform providers),
 - NGOs or city stakeholders working on citizen engagement,
 - EU universities with complementary expertise (e.g., behavioural economics).
- Propose PhD projects based on:
 - AI personalisation in energy interfaces,
 - Gamified tools for user engagement,
 - Societal trust in algorithmic sustainability systems.

3. Staff Exchanges (SE)

Short- to medium-term secondments of research and innovation staff across sectors or countries.

EU-DREAM's value:

- Provides a platform for testing tools in applied contexts (municipalities, SMEs, DIHs).
- Offers expertise in modular architectures, interface evaluation, and digital transformation.
- Offers expertise in market analysis, as well as validation of business models.
- Offers practical experience in AI applications for energy and sustainability, as well as exposure to cross-disciplinary research environments.

What should be done:

- Identify partner organisations (e.g., DIHs, public utilities, startups).
- Structure exchanges around:
 - Co-development of new platform modules,
 - User testing and participatory co-design,
 - AI explainability models in energy markets.

4. COFUND

Co-financing regional, national, or institutional fellowship programs.

What should be done:

- Explore collaborations with the AUTH central administration to:
 - Launch a **digital sustainability COFUND programme**.
 - Include energy platform projects, AI ethics, and digital inclusion.

Scientific & Training Value

The WP4 and WP6 research environment offers:

- A real-world testbed to study human-AI interaction in energy systems.
- A training ground for skills in digital interface design, data science, algorithm deployment, and energy systems thinking.
- Opportunities for secondments with energy communities, city partners, and DIHs.

It aligns strongly with MSCA priorities in:

- Green and digital transitions (European Green Deal & Digital Decade),
- Societal engagement with science,
- Equipping researchers with transferable, future-facing skills.

European Institute of Innovation and Technology - Knowledge and Innovation Communities

EU-DREAM is well-positioned to contribute to the objectives of the EI and its KICs by advancing innovation, business creation, and education in the energy sector. The project brings together expertise in the development of user-centric digital energy platforms, energy literacy tools, digital twin technologies, and data-driven business models. Through coordinated research and pilot activities, EU-DREAM can support the rapid prototyping, demonstration, and scaling of low-carbon energy solutions, as well as generate strategic insights into consumer behaviour and new business models. These strengths foster cross-sectoral collaboration and accelerate the adoption of sustainable innovations across Europe, which aligns closely with the missions of KICs such as:

- **EIT InnoEnergy** (sustainable energy)
- **EIT Digital** (advanced digital systems and platforms)
- **EIT Climate-KIC** (climate innovation)

Alignment Between EU-DREAM and EIT KICs

➤ EIT InnoEnergy

- **WP4's energy marketplace** aligns with InnoEnergy's mission to accelerate innovative business models for flexible, prosumer-based energy systems.

- The platform's capacity to simulate and support **P2P energy trading, grid services, and AI-based consumer engagement** fits directly into InnoEnergy's interest in real-world digital energy entrepreneurship.
- It can be analysed the economic and social viability conditions of energy business models.
- **WP2** and **WP7** bring deep expertise in **digital energy systems, AI, and microgrids**, particularly on digital twin models, simulation frameworks, AI tools, and NLP-based interfaces.

Actions:

- Propose a **co-validation initiative** where the WP4 platform is tested by EIT InnoEnergy-affiliated startups or pilot sites.
- Apply for InnoEnergy's **Business Creation Services** to support the commercialisation of platform components or spin-offs.
- Collaborate on pilot initiatives and demonstration projects that integrate advanced AI techniques (such as predictive analytics, forecasting models, etc.) into innovative energy solutions.
- Collaborate on pilot and demonstration projects that leverage rapid prototyping, advanced simulation, and AI-driven control algorithms to accelerate the development and deployment of digital solutions for decarbonising local energy systems.
- Provide market viability analysis through evidence-based analysis on the potential adoption rates and profitability of new business models being considered by InnoEnergy-supported startups.
- Offer insights from UCLM's simulation framework that can help startups identify key market barriers and consumer acceptance issues before committing to full-scale development, providing a de-risking innovation.

➤ EIT Digital

- WP4 develops a **modular, interoperable digital architecture** for smart interfaces, personalised analytics, and service integration — all core areas for EIT Digital.
- WP6 contributes to **digital user experience innovation**, including AI explainability, user adaptation, and inclusive design.
- Expertise in consumer responsiveness to AI-enhanced services.

Actions:

- Engage in **EIT Digital's Accelerator Programme**, presenting WP4-based solutions for scaling and market entry.
- Propose joint **use cases or demonstrators** around energy-user interaction in smart cities, public buildings, or regional clusters.
- Co-develop educational programs and training materials on AI applications in energy systems.
- Share research findings on human-AI interaction regarding consumer trust, aversion to control, and the acceptance of AI-driven automation in the energy sector. This knowledge can help EIT Digital-affiliated companies design more user-centric and effective digital platforms.

- Provide detailed Data-driven consumer profiles (archetypes) based on behavioural modelling, which can be used by startups to better understand and segment their target customers.

➤ EIT Climate-KIC

- WP6 contributes directly to Climate-KIC's focus on **behavioural change, citizen engagement, and climate literacy**.
- The WP4 platform can provide tools for **visualising emissions, setting personal goals**, and engaging users in collective climate actions — a perfect fit for Climate-KIC's Living Labs and Deep Demonstrations.
- Supporting climate literacy initiatives through engagement in workshops, contributing practical, scalable solutions that empower citizens and organisations in their climate-neutral transition.
- Supporting behavioural change and citizen engagement to drive climate action through UCLM's ABM framework, which is designed to simulate the effectiveness of different engagement strategies.

Actions:

- Submit a proposal to **Climate-KIC's community engagement funding calls**, linking platform tools to local sustainability campaigns or municipal climate strategies.
- Offer to integrate WP6 tools into Climate-KIC's **climate innovation education pilots**.
- Assessment of Engagement Strategies, analysing the potential impact of different incentive schemes or community campaigns on consumer behaviour, providing an evidence base for Climate-KIC's Living Labs and Deep Demonstrations.
- Policy Scenario Analysis provides insights on how different policy frameworks could accelerate (or hinder) the adoption of pro-climate behaviours at the community level.

Green Powered Future Mission

EU-DREAM partners bring complementary strengths to the objectives of the Green Powered Future Mission (GPFM), particularly under Pillar 2, which focuses on System Flexibility and Market Design, and Pillar 3, which addresses data and digitalisation for system integration. Through the development of a modular, AI-ready digital platform, the project supports real-time user interaction, decentralised energy participation, and robust interoperability via open APIs. This architecture not only enables integration with energy system operators and flexibility markets but also accommodates a wide range of user profiles, including consumers, prosumers, and aggregators, addressing key challenges in distributed energy resource (DER) integration.

EU-DREAM Scientific and Technical Alignment

➤ System Integration via User Participation

- WP4 platform enables **active demand-side integration** by supporting **personalised energy services**, including flexibility response and energy trading.
- The platform accommodates heterogeneous user profiles (consumers, prosumers, aggregators) and reflects **DER** integration challenges.

➤ **Data Interoperability and Architecture**

- The WP4 platform is designed with a **modular architecture and RESTful APIs**, facilitating integration with external energy systems, including grid operators, smart meter infrastructures, and market platforms.
- Supports real-time data exchange and enhances capacity for cross-sectoral collaboration.

➤ **AI-Based System Intelligence**

- AI models for user profiling, forecasting, and optimisation support **dynamic energy scheduling** and **consumer behaviour prediction** — critical for system-wide coordination under high renewable energy sources (RES) penetration.
- Living labs infrastructure for predictive control, user-interactive optimisation, and natural language processing interfaces that connect users with system intelligence in real time.

➤ **Behavioural Research and Socio-Technical Business Models**

- Researches consumer behaviour and socio-technical business models, strengthening contributions to Pillar 2 and Pillar 3.
- Models user response to new flexibility business models, closing the gap between technical potential and actual participation.
- Explores digital tools and data-driven approaches for more integrated and user-centric energy systems, including P2P models for system integration at the community level.

➤ **Participation in GPFM Activities**

- Focuses on AI, interoperability, and inclusive system design to both contribute to and benefit from Europe's transition toward a flexible, digital, and integrated energy system.

Recommended Actions

1. Position the platform as a testbed for system-level digital integration

Action:

- Document and promote WP4's technical stack (data models, APIs, control layers) as a **reference architecture** for consumer-centric integration in smart grid pilot programs.
- Provide access to a **sandbox version** of the platform for aggregators or research partners working on GPFM-aligned initiatives.

2. Enable real-time flexibility interface prototypes

Action:

- Implement and demonstrate **user-side flexibility modules** (e.g., automated notifications, consumption rescheduling tools) that could integrate with **local or national flexibility markets**.
- Develop and showcase behaviour-based flexibility metrics, factoring in trust in AI, aversion to control, and economic incentives.

3. Contribute to data governance and standardisation discussions

Action:

- Participate in **EU-level working groups** or coordination actions on energy data spaces, consent frameworks, and interoperability (e.g., BRIDGE initiative, InterConnect community).
- Share WP4 findings on data accessibility, user control, and privacy in distributed energy services.
- Offer methodological guidance and best practices for the ethical, secure, and effective integration of heterogeneous energy datasets into digital platforms and data ecosystems.
- Provide evidence-based perspectives on consumer concerns and willingness to share data in exchange for improved services.

4. Integrate platform insights into energy system simulations

Action:

- Collaborate with system modelers to **incorporate user behaviour patterns** and platform-generated flexibility metrics into larger system operation or market design models.
- Publish comparative analyses of different market designs (such as P2P, FaaS, DR-Flex), assessing their effectiveness in both economic terms and in encouraging voluntary consumer participation.

5. Disseminate findings through Pillar 3-aligned channels

Action:

- Publish the architecture, AI methodologies, and user interaction findings in **system integration journals** (e.g., *Applied Energy*, *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*).
- Share results from the UCLM's ABM framework demonstrating how **digital platform interactions shape consumer decisions** and system dynamics.

6. Advance standards and best practices

Action:

- Contribute to standardisation efforts supporting the integration of diverse energy datasets into secure and ethical digital platforms.
- Develop and disseminate guidance for AI-driven forecasting, predictive maintenance, and optimization algorithms to enhance grid flexibility and integration of renewables.

7. Facilitate stakeholder engagement and capacity building

Action:

- Host capacity-building workshops and expert exchanges, particularly at the living labs, to connect research with system-level deployment and innovation.
- Organize workshops and training initiatives focused on the application of AI in energy contexts.

Alliance for AI, IoT and Edge Continuum Innovation

Alliance for AI, IoT and Edge Continuum Innovation (AIOTI) has WGs focused on **smart energy systems, data spaces, edge infrastructure, and AI-human interaction**, making it a natural ecosystem for collaboration with the EU-DREAM's research.

Strategic Alignment Between EU-DREAM and AIOTI Objectives

➤ Interoperable Edge-Ready Platform Architecture

- Develops a **modular, open architecture platform** with clear APIs that can integrate external services and models.
- Design platforms **compatible with edge environments**, supporting low-latency operations and decentralised user participation.

Actions:

- Document the platform's technical architecture and publish it as a **case study or reference architecture** within AIOTI's **Working Groups IoT Architecture** or **Smart Energy**.

➤ Digital Twin and Microgrid Innovation

- Through Living Labs, EU-DREAM provides real-world testbeds for digital twin architectures, microgrid simulation, and user interaction with NLP-based interfaces.
- These activities align with AIOTI's priorities for advancing edge-AI convergence and real-world validation of intelligent energy systems.

Actions:

- Present digital twin methodologies, simulation frameworks, and microgrid deployment results in relevant AIOTI WGs and knowledge-sharing events.
- Share best practices for integrating AI-driven decision-making and predictive control in distributed energy environments.

➤ AI-Enabled User Services for Energy Systems

- WP4 platform incorporates **AI-driven decision-support tools**, adaptive interfaces, and natural language processing (NLP) to support diverse energy users.

- These technologies align with AIOTI's efforts to define **human-centric, trustworthy AI applications** in IoT-enabled environments.

Actions:

- Present the platform's personalisation methods and user models to the **AIOTI Working Group AI and Semantic Interoperability**.
- Contribute to technical papers or position statements on **AI-assisted human decision-making in critical infrastructure**.
- Provide simulation-based analysis of **user acceptance, aversion to control, and business model effectiveness for inclusion** in AIOTI position papers.

➤ Open Standards, Ethics, and Governance

- WP4 promotes **user-side transparency, data control, and platform modularity** in line with AIOTI's goals on **responsible digital infrastructure**.

Actions:

- Provide technical feedback to AIOTI's work on **open standards for smart energy interfaces**, especially around **API harmonisation, consent mechanisms, and ethical AI for energy autonomy**.
- Participate in consultations, white papers, and workshops under **AIOTI's cross-sector governance forums**.

➤ Stakeholder Engagement and Knowledge Transfer

- EU-DREAM's living labs, capacity-building initiatives, and socio-technical research foster broad **engagement and practical knowledge-sharing**, complementing AIOTI's mission to bridge research, policy, and innovation.

Actions:

- Host workshops, expert exchanges, and capacity-building events on AI and IoT in energy, targeting both technical and non-technical stakeholders.
- Share validated use cases, pilot results, and evidence-based recommendations with AIOTI working groups and the wider community.

By advancing these actions, EU-DREAM ensures a productive and mutually reinforcing relationship with AIOTI, helping to accelerate the development and deployment of resilient, user-centric, and interoperable AI-IoT-edge solutions for the energy transition in Europe, where citizens are not just consumers, but **data-informed, system-integrated actors**.

Clusters of Digital Projects

EU-DREAM's work on digital twin models and modular, interoperable, and AI-powered digital platforms for energy services is highly relevant to several leading digital project clusters. These efforts align with key thematic areas, including the digitalisation of the energy system, human-

centric digital infrastructure, data governance and interoperability, smart consumer engagement, and the development of edge-AI platforms and energy data services.

Thematic Alignment with Digital Project Clusters

➤ **Digitalisation of Energy System Cluster (e.g., BRIDGE, InterConnect, SYNERGY, edgeFLEX):**

- Implements **user-centric modules** for energy services (consumption monitoring, participation in energy marketplaces).
- Offers **API-based integration** with external systems.
- Supports **data sovereignty and explainability**, aligned with the EU's Digitalisation of Energy Action Plan.
- Supports interoperable, real-time modelling of energy assets and behaviours through a digital twin framework, enabling system-level optimization and predictive control.

Actions:

- Map WP4's architecture and features to existing energy digitalisation cluster projects.
- Share findings with projects like **InterConnect**, **PLATOON**, or **edgeFLEX**, which also explore AI, IoT, and edge/cloud integration in energy systems.

➤ **AI/Data/Edge Cluster (e.g., AI4EU, i-ENERGY, PHOENIX, AI-SPRINT):**

- Integrates **AI models for energy forecasting, personalization, and system control**.
- **Edge-ready architecture** suitable for local deployment and fast feedback.
- Tools supporting **trustworthy, explainable AI** for decision support.

Actions:

- Offer the WP4 platform as a **test case or reference implementation** in working groups on **AI in energy and IoT**.
- Join workshops or coordination actions to help define **best practices for edge AI deployments** in citizen-facing platforms.

➤ **Citizen-Centric Digital Platforms Cluster (e.g., DOMOS, SMART-BEAR, USERCHI)**

- Advances **energy literacy** and user engagement by developing digital tools for societal involvement in energy, climate, and smart services.
- Promotes participatory design, co-creation, and gamification strategies **for inclusive platform development**.

Actions:

- Contribute to joint **position papers** on inclusive platform design, user adaptation, and co-creation processes.
- Propose cross-project experiments using shared engagement methodologies (e.g., participatory design, gamification).

➤ **Cross-Cluster Relevance and Innovation**

- Supports interoperable, real-time modelling of energy assets and behaviours through digital twin frameworks, enabling system-level optimization and predictive control.
- Facilitates modular integration with IoT infrastructures, cloud/edge data flows, and the use of AI for scenario simulation and local control.
- Enables real-world user interaction and co-creation in living lab environments, relevant to citizen-involved technology development.

Actions:

- Demonstrate the platform and digital twin models in relevant cluster working groups and knowledge exchange activities.
- Share results, lessons learned, and methodologies to foster cross-project innovation and the advancement of digital and energy research across Europe.

Through these coordinated actions, EU-DREAM actively supports collaboration and knowledge transfer across multiple digital project clusters, helping to accelerate the digital transformation and user empowerment in Europe's energy landscape.

Coordinating Actions Related to the Digitalisation of the Energy System

EU-DREAM contributes directly to the objectives of the EU's Digitalisation of the Energy System Action Plan through the development of scalable, user-centric, and AI-integrated platforms that incorporate key principles such as interoperability, consumer empowerment, smart energy services, AI and edge computing integration, and digital inclusion.

1. Interoperable and Modular Digital Infrastructure

EU-DREAM is advancing platform architectures that enable seamless data portability and API-level integration across diverse energy systems. The project's approach facilitates the secure and efficient exchange of information, supporting the interoperability required by a digitalised energy ecosystem, as described:

- Platform design is modular, enabling easy adaptation and extension to new energy applications and market actors.
- Robust support for open APIs ensures compatibility with a wide range of coordination platforms, such as ETIP SNET and Data4Energy.
- Active participation in cross-project interoperability pilots helps align data schemas, harmonise communication protocols, and foster system-wide integration.
- Adoption of emerging standards and best practices promotes scalable, future-proof digital infrastructure for Europe's energy transition.

2. Human-Centric and Participatory Digitalisation

EU-DREAM is committed to designing digital energy solutions that are truly centred on people, ensuring accessibility, transparency, and usability for all, including underserved groups. The

project integrates user training, behavioural insights, and participatory design to create platforms that reflect real needs and foster active engagement, as follows:

- Focuses on enhancing data transparency, user control, and platform usability for citizens and communities.
- Incorporates behavioural modelling and participatory methods to better understand and serve diverse user groups.
- Integrates behavioural theories, such as COM-B, to inform the simulation and design of inclusive energy systems.
- Contributes methodological papers, case studies, and analyses to working groups and policy forums, sharing expertise on inclusive design, energy literacy, and factors influencing user acceptance, such as trust in AI and transparency.
- Promotes a participatory digitalisation process that supports broader acceptance and social impact of digital innovation in energy.

3. Testing, Validation, and Reuse of Results

EU-DREAM's platform and educational resources are designed for adaptability and integration within broader European digitalisation efforts. These assets are well-suited for deployment in shared demonstrators, federated testbeds, and reference implementations supported by Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs).

- Provides a robust testing environment for joint activities within digitalisation clusters, enabling collaborative experimentation and benchmarking.
- Engages in partnerships with coordinating projects to scale evaluation protocols, facilitate dataset sharing, and validate citizen-facing digital interfaces.
- Supports reuse and knowledge transfer by contributing tested solutions and methodologies to the wider innovation community, accelerating adoption and impact across Europe's energy sector.

4. Technical Expertise and Best Practices for AI-Enabled Energy Solutions

EU-DREAM is positioned to advance the digitalisation of the energy system by offering deep technical know-how and sharing best-practice insights related to AI-enabled tools for energy management.

- Delivers expertise on the deployment and optimisation of AI solutions within the energy sector.
- Shares practical lessons learned to inform the secure, effective integration of advanced digital technologies.

5. Methodological Guidance for Secure and Ethical Data Use

The project is committed to upholding transparency, security, and ethical standards in data-driven energy management by:

- Providing methodological recommendations for the responsible use of data in AI-based energy platforms.

- Advocating for transparent data governance and privacy-preserving practices, ensuring trust and compliance in digital energy systems.

6. Knowledge Exchange, Stakeholder Engagement, and Policy Alignment

EU-DREAM actively advances the sector's digital transformation by promoting knowledge sharing, stakeholder engagement, and policy alignment throughout the European energy landscape. The project supports the broad dissemination of best practices and practical experiences, ensuring that innovation is harmonised and impactful. For instance:

- Organises and participates in workshops, expert exchanges, and collaborative forums focused on the application and impact of AI and digital tools in energy systems.
- Develops and shares technical guidelines, methodological frameworks, and demonstrator outcomes for interoperable digital twin deployment and digital energy solutions.
- Engages in ongoing dialogue and capacity building among stakeholders, reinforcing the successful adoption of innovative digital solutions.
- Participates in cross-project workshops, task forces, and EU-level coordination initiatives on digitalisation, AI governance, and edge/cloud integration.
- Collaborates with coordination bodies such as BRIDGE, AI4EU, and other networks to support knowledge exchange and foster harmonised innovation and policy development across Europe.

7. Consumer Empowerment

EU-DREAM's research contributes to giving citizens an active and informed role in the evolving energy market, fully supporting the objectives of the EU's Digitalisation of the Energy System Action Plan. The project analyses and develops approaches such as peer-to-peer (P2P) trading and flexibility services that facilitate consumer participation and agency. As a consequence:

- Comparative analyses can be published to assess the impact of different business models on consumer empowerment and economic benefits.
- Simulation-based case studies can be provided to illustrate for policymakers and local communities how innovative business models can increase energy autonomy at the community level.

8. Digital Inclusion

Promoting an inclusive digital transition is central to EU-DREAM's work. The project uses behavioural archetypes and socio-technical modelling to understand the diverse needs, challenges, and adoption barriers faced by different segments of the population in the context of digital energy services. The project can:

- Analyse the obstacles encountered by specific consumer profiles, including those with lower trust in technology or non-economic priorities.

- Offer evidence-based recommendations for service design and incentive policies, supporting the development of more inclusive, effective solutions that broaden digital participation and leave no one behind.

9. Advanced Digital Twin Modelling for Energy Systems

EU-DREAM is advancing modular and scalable digital twin architectures to support the real-time simulation, forecasting, and optimization of smart energy infrastructures. These solutions enable dynamic, adaptive modelling and enhance the flexibility and resilience of the energy system, which can foster:

- Integration of diverse data sources, including IoT devices, smart meters, weather data, and user behaviour, to build self-adaptive models.
- Support of edge deployment for low-latency feedback and control in distributed environments.
- Utilisation of semantic interoperability standards (e.g., SAREF, CIM) to promote cross-platform integration and seamless communication.

10. AI-Augmented Predictive Control and Optimization

The project combines digital twin models with advanced AI and machine learning algorithms to provide predictive analytics and intelligent decision support for energy management, allowing:

- Implementation of reinforcement learning and hybrid AI methods for demand-side flexibility, forecasting, and anomaly detection.
- Prioritisation of trustworthy and explainable AI, ensuring transparent system behaviour and enabling human-in-the-loop control.
- Contribution of technical validation and verification processes for safety-critical applications in smart grids and local energy communities.

11. Living Lab Validation and User-Centric Integration

Validation of digital twin and AI solutions occurs within EU-DREAM's living labs, where technologies are tested and refined in real-world energy environments that integrate IoT infrastructures and involve active end-user participation. Thus, it is possible to:

- Evaluate energy services under actual operating conditions, including applications in smart homes, flexibility services, and home energy management systems (HEMS).
- Facilitate ongoing user feedback loops to optimise model performance and usability.
- Co-design energy literacy tools and citizen-centric data governance approaches to ensure ethical data use and promote social acceptance.

Conclusions

This deliverable has provided a comprehensive overview of the cooperation activities undertaken by the EU-DREAM project during its first year, highlighting the strategic importance of collaborative efforts across complementary EU projects, the BRIDGE initiative, and a broad portfolio of European instruments and initiatives. Through its active participation in alliances such as the E-ENERGY cluster and the four BRIDGE Working Groups, EU-DREAM has both contributed to and benefited from the exchange of knowledge, best practices, and innovative solutions within the European research and innovation landscape.

EU-DREAM's engagement with the E-ENERGY cluster has established a dynamic model for project clustering, joint branding, and the co-development of resources that amplify the impact of consumer-centric digital innovation in the energy sector. This collaborative environment has enabled partners to pool expertise, align outreach strategies, and co-create tools and methodologies that advance energy literacy and citizen empowerment at scale.

Participation in the BRIDGE initiative, spanning Business Model, Regulation, Consumer and Citizen Engagement, and Data Management Working Groups, has enabled EU-DREAM to both shape and respond to emerging trends in energy digitalisation. The project's contributions have supported the development of robust, scalable business models, fostered regulatory dialogue on flexibility and market integration, driven progress in inclusive and ethical stakeholder engagement, and accelerated the adoption of interoperable, standards-based data management practices. Lessons learned from these engagements have informed the project's own methodology and are already influencing future work, ensuring continued relevance and impact.

Beyond these core collaborations, EU-DREAM has established meaningful connections with other major EU initiatives and instruments, including Erasmus+, Digital Innovation Hubs, the European Climate Pact, the EC Digital Education Action Plan, ERC, MSCA, EIT KICs, and others. By leveraging its digital platforms, living labs, and research outcomes, the project has promoted capacity building, interdisciplinary knowledge transfer, and the adoption of digital skills and solutions in diverse sectors and communities across Europe.

Throughout these activities, EU-DREAM has demonstrated that cooperation is not simply an added value, but a fundamental driver of effective digital and green transition. The project's approach, based on open sharing, joint experimentation, and mutual learning, has laid the groundwork for more resilient, inclusive, and scalable innovations. Key achievements include the deployment of advanced AI and digital twin technologies, the empowerment of consumers as active participants in energy markets, and the broad dissemination of best practices in digital education, climate action, and policy support.

Looking forward, EU-DREAM will continue to build on these foundations by deepening its cooperation with established and emerging initiatives, enhancing cross-sectoral synergies, and translating collaborative insights into concrete impacts for European citizens and communities.

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Appendix – E-ENERGY Brochure

In the Appendix, the latest E-ENERGY Brochure (*“Consumers at the heart of the energy transition through digital innovation”*) is reported.

